

Scaling of SARS-CoV-2 Genomic Divergence with Cumulative Infections During the COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic constitutes the largest natural experiment in viral evolution ever observed. Unlike previous analyses that have used time as the independent variable, this study uses cumulative infections — a more biologically meaningful measure of replication opportunity that is not confounded by variation in transmission intensity. Analysis of 1,280 SARS-CoV-2 genomes from three years of global transmission paired with cumulative infection estimates from the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME) found that substitutions relative to Wuhan-Hu-1 accumulated at a rate of 8.9 per billion human infection events.

The observed pandemic scaling relationship suggests that producing ~1,000 fixed nucleotide differences would require replication opportunities comparable to roughly 100 billion human infections. An intentionally conservative model based on confirmed COVID-19 cases, well-established as an underestimate of total infections, and substitution data that have not been filtered to remove extreme values likely to represent sequencing artifacts or transient polymorphisms predicts that billions of infections would be required. These results provide an empirical benchmark for the replication opportunity required to generate large numbers of substitutions under pandemic-scale human transmission suggesting that the divergence observed among known sarbecoviruses would require either very large host populations, extended evolutionary timescales, or both under conditions comparable to pandemic-scale human transmission.

Introduction

RNA viruses are often described as rapidly evolving, reflecting high per-replication mutation rates and large population sizes.¹ However, mutation rates alone do not determine the pace at which adaptive genetic change accumulates in circulating viral lineages. Long-term evolutionary divergence depends on the fixation of advantageous mutations, a process constrained by purifying selection, transmission bottlenecks, and epistatic interactions across the genome.^{2,3} Direct empirical evidence on the rates at which divergence accumulates across large viral populations has historically been limited by the scale of viral outbreaks.

The COVID-19 pandemic provides an unprecedented natural experiment in viral evolution. Since late 2019, SARS-CoV-2 has spread globally under heterogeneous epidemiological and immunological conditions, while extensive genomic surveillance has made it possible to track viral evolution in near real time.⁴ This combination of pandemic-scale replication and dense genomic sampling offers a unique opportunity to empirically bound the pace at which adaptive genetic divergence accumulates under sustained transmission, providing an empirical calibration of the relationship between replication opportunity and genomic divergence in a coronavirus population.. This framework also provides a context for interpreting genomic differences among related sarbecoviruses and their evolutionary implications.

Previous analyses of SARS-CoV-2 evolutionary rates have typically used time as the independent variable. However, substitutions accumulate through replication events rather than through the passage of time. Cumulative infections therefore represent a more biologically meaningful measure of replication opportunity, and one that is not confounded by the substantial variation in transmission intensity observed across the pandemic period. The closest known sarbecovirus relative of SARS-CoV-2 is BANAL-52⁵ from Laos, which differs from the Wuhan-Hu-1 reference genome by approximately 950 fixed nucleotide differences. The closest sequence identified in Wuhan, RaTG13⁶ differs by approximately 1,100 fixed nucleotide differences. The scaling relationship derived from the pandemic data can be used to estimate the number of infection events required to generate 1,000 substitutions along a viral lineage.

Methods

SARS-CoV-2 genomic data were obtained from the Nextstrain open SARS-CoV-2 dataset⁷. The primary analysis used the mutation counts provided in the standard Nextstrain phylogeny, which represents a curated set of substitutions inferred along the phylogenetic path from the Wuhan-Hu-1 root to each terminal genome. The Nextstrain pipeline applies multiple quality filters and phylogenetic reconciliation steps to remove sequencing artifacts, recurrent mutations at highly homoplastic sites, and other features that could distort phylogenetic inference. The resulting mutation counts represent substitutions relative to the Wuhan-Hu-1 reference genome inferred along the phylogenetic path from the root to each sampled

genome. In this manuscript these counts are referred to as genomic substitutions or genomic divergence relative to Wuhan-Hu-1. These filtered mutation counts were used to generate the central estimate of the relationship between genomic divergence and cumulative infections.

The analysis included the terminal genomes represented in the Nextstrain dataset over the study period, with each genome paired to the cumulative infection estimate for its sampling date. No additional downsampling or deduplication was applied beyond the standard Nextstrain pipeline.

Estimates of cumulative global SARS-CoV-2 daily infections were obtained from the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME).⁸ Each genome observation was then paired with the cumulative infection estimate corresponding to its sampling date.

Genomic divergence from the Wuhan-Hu-1 strain was plotted against cumulative global infection estimates. Because zero infections must correspond to zero divergence, a linear regression constrained through the origin was used to estimate the relationship between cumulative infections and substitutions:

$$M = kI$$

where M represents substitutions relative to the Wuhan-Hu-1 reference genome and I represents cumulative global infection events in billions. Because the ancestral genome corresponds to zero cumulative infections, the regression was constrained to pass through the origin.

The equation above was used to estimate the number of human infections required to generate 1000 substitutions along a sarbecovirus lineage. In addition to the central estimate, a second estimate incorporated the most conservative possible assumptions to provide a lower bound estimate on the scale of the replication opportunities required.

To evaluate the most conservative possible scaling relationship, an alternative dataset was constructed using unfiltered mutation counts derived directly from the full set of substitutions observed along each terminal path in the phylogeny prior to the Nextstrain filtering steps. These counts include recurrent mutations, homoplastic sites, and other substitutions that may reflect sequencing noise or transient polymorphisms rather than lineage-defining changes. Because this approach tends to inflate apparent divergence for a given point in time, it produces a steeper relationship between mutations and cumulative infections. When used to extrapolate evolutionary scaling, this dataset therefore provides an extreme lower-bound estimate of the number of infection events required to generate a given level of genomic divergence. Because this alternative dataset simultaneously inflates apparent divergence and

underestimates total infections, it should be interpreted as a deliberately biased floor rather than as a competing central estimate.

Both datasets were analyzed using the same regression framework relating substitutions relative to the Wuhan-Hu-1 reference genome to cumulative infection estimates corresponding to the sampling date of each genome.

Data processing was conducted using Python (version 3.x) with pandas and NumPy (script available in Supplementary materials). Figures and regression visualizations were generated using Microsoft Excel.

Substitution counts from Nextstrain data through February 2026 were used to validate the model projection over the three years since the most recent infection estimates were generated by IHME.

Results

Nextstrain and IHME yielded overlapping data for the period from February 5, 2020 through February 28, 2023 to produce a data set with 1,280 viral genomes aligned by date with cumulative global SARS-CoV-2 infections. Across the full set of sampled genomes, genomic divergence increased predictably with cumulative global SARS-CoV-2 infections (Figure 1). When individual genome observations were plotted against cumulative infections, the relationship was well described by a linear scaling model.

Figure 1. Substitutions in the SARS-CoV-2 lineages as a function of cumulative global transmission. Each point represents an individual viral genome sampled in the Nextstrain dataset. The number of genomic substitutions relative to the Wuhan-Hu-1 reference genome is plotted against cumulative

estimated global SARS-CoV-2 infections. A linear regression equation, $M = 8.9 I$, provides a close fit to the evolutionary trajectory observed across the dataset ($R^2 = 0.96$).

Least-squares linear regression yielded the relationship:

$$M = 8.9 I$$

$$(R^2 = 0.96),$$

where M is the number of substitutions and I is the number of infections in billions.

A more recent data point provides an opportunity to test the projection derived from the linear regression shown in Figure 1. SARS-CoV-2 lineages in March of 2026 differ from the Wuhan reference genome by ~ 180 substitutions. The regression model suggests this would require ~ 20 billion infections or ~ 2 billion per year since 2022

Reliable global estimates of cumulative infection events since 2022 are not available because routine testing largely collapsed as the pandemic evolved. Nevertheless, it is possible to construct reasonable bounds for the total number of infection events that have likely occurred since the end of 2022 and compare those bounds to the value predicted by the regression relationship.

By the end of 2022, modeling by the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation suggested that cumulative global SARS-CoV-2 infection events had already reached approximately 14 billion, including reinfections. Independent evidence suggests this figure may itself represent an upper-bound estimate. For example, survey-based estimates of infection frequency imply roughly 1.25 infections per person during the pandemic period, corresponding to approximately 10 billion global infection events, substantially lower than the IHME estimate. Even if the higher IHME figure is retained as a baseline, simple epidemiologic bounds constrain subsequent transmission. A theoretical upper bound would assume that the three years since 2022 matched transmission intensity observed during the entire pandemic-period, yielding approximately 28 billion cumulative infection events—an assumption that appears implausible given declining surveillance, rising immunity, and the absence of pandemic-scale waves. A more generous assumption—that every person in the global population experienced one additional infection since 2022—would produce roughly 22 billion cumulative infection events. Against this background, the regression projection indicating approximately 25 billion infection events corresponding to currently circulating lineages (~ 180 substitutions relative to Wuhan-Hu-1) lies at or above plausible epidemiologic estimates. This suggests that the fitted relationship between infection events and genomic divergence is, if anything, somewhat steep, and that the extrapolated requirement of roughly 110 billion infection events to reach $\sim 1,000$ substitutions along a lineage is a reasonable estimate.

The second data set based on unfiltered Nextstrain mutation data and confirmed infection counts provides a much lower estimate of approximately 4 billion infections to reach 1,000

substitutions along a lineage. This is almost certainly an underestimate. From the outset of the pandemic it became clear that confirmed and reported cases capture only a fraction of total infections. An influential early seroprevalence study suggested under-ascertainment was on the order of 50–85-fold.⁹ This estimate should therefore be interpreted as an extremely conservative lower bound, not an alternative central estimate.

Figure 2. Projected human infections required to generate ~1,000 substitutions along a SARS-CoV-2 lineage, comparable to the genomic divergence observed among related sarbecoviruses, based on most plausible and most conservative model assumptions.

Discussion

The COVID-19 pandemic provides an unprecedented empirical record of viral evolution occurring under sustained global transmission. By linking genomic divergence to estimates of cumulative infection, this analysis provides a quantitative framework for evaluating how rapidly

substitutions accumulate during pandemic-scale viral spread. Across the first three years of the pandemic, substitutions accumulated at approximately 8.9 substitutions per billion infection events. This pattern suggests that, despite the high mutation rate of RNA viruses, the accumulation of substitutions in circulating lineages is constrained, presumably due to broader evolutionary processes such as purifying selection, transmission bottlenecks, and epistatic interactions across the genome.

The scaling relationship observed during the pandemic provides an empirical calibration of the replication opportunity required for large numbers of substitutions to accumulate in circulating coronaviruses.

Several limitations should be considered. Estimates of cumulative global infections are derived from epidemiological models and therefore contain uncertainty, particularly during the early phases of the pandemic when case detection was limited and surveillance systems were still developing. In addition, genomic sampling is uneven across geographic regions and time periods, reflecting differences in sequencing capacity and surveillance intensity. Although the large number of genomes available provides a broad representation of circulating diversity, the dataset does not represent a uniform sample of global viral populations. Finally, extrapolating pandemic-scale divergence dynamics to longer evolutionary timescales should be interpreted cautiously, as evolutionary processes operating in wildlife reservoirs may differ from those observed during sustained human transmission.

The conservative model puts a lower bound on these estimates, suggesting that ~1,000 substitutions along a viral lineage of a sarbecovirus would require replication opportunities greater than those provided by 4 billion human infections and probably closer to the equivalent of 100 billion human infections. It should also be noted that these estimates are derived from human infections, which generate orders of magnitude more viral replication^{10–12} per infection than infections in small mammals.^{13–15} To the extent that this scaling relationship is applied to viral evolution in wildlife reservoir species, the number of infection events required to generate equivalent genomic divergence would be correspondingly larger. This distinction also highlights a broader limitation of time-based evolutionary rate estimates, which cannot be translated across host species. An infection-based rate, by contrast, provides a unit that is in principle adjustable for differences in replication opportunity per infection event, making cross-species comparisons more tractable even if the precise correction factors remain uncertain.

These constraints help frame the evolutionary context of SARS-CoV-2 and related sarbecoviruses and provide a quantitative benchmark for interpreting genomic divergence within this group. Together, these observations suggest that generating the level of genomic divergence observed among closely related sarbecoviruses would require replication opportunities spanning very large host populations over multiple generations and extended evolutionary timescales.

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